

Pacific Salmon at a Crossroads A StoryMap

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About This StoryMap

This StoryMap serves as an informative tool for general audiences, offering a visual and accessible guide to the challenges Pacific salmon face due to urban stormwater runoff and climate change. Through engaging content and interactive elements, it highlights the importance of these species, the impacts of stressors, and potential solutions. This poster provides a brief outline of the topics covered, but please scan the QR code to view the full story!

Climate Change

- Rising stream temperatures, reduced in-stream flows (less water), and increased habitat disruption from storm events
- While these stressors already pose a challenge for salmon recovery, when combined with polluted runoff, the impacts may worsen

Importance of Salmon

- Central to the culture, ecology, and economy of western North America
- Urban development and climate change are threatening the recovery of populations, many of which are at historically low abundances

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Implications

Mysterious Mortalities

- Salmon returning to spawn began to behave erratically, swimming in circles and gaping before losing equilibrium and dying within a few hours
- Coho spawner mortalities sometimes exceed 90% in developing watersheds

Green Infrastructure Solutions

- Using methods that filter or otherwise capture and remove pollutants is one of the few options for salmon habitat conservation and restoration
- Simple and inexpensive treatment methods can be very effective in terms of both removing pollutants and protecting sensitive species

The Discovery of 6PPD-q

- In 2020, a research team ground conventional tires into small particles, and when added to water, Coho exposed to this mixture experienced the same mortality syndrome described above
- Toxicity was prevented by pre-filtering the mixture through experimental rain gardens
- Identified tire additive 6PPD, and more specifically, 6PPD-quinone (6PPD-q) as the driver of the mysterious mortality syndrome

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